

Institution: CCE – RVV

Date: 01.07.2020

Interviewee: Judge Katelijne Declerck (KD)

Interviewers: Zoé Crine (ZC); Francesca Raimondo (FR)

Auditor: Laura Cools (LC)

Language: English

In reading this transcription, please, note that the interview was held in English, but that the interviewee is a Dutch-speaker and the interviewers are not English native speakers. The person that has transcribed the interview is not a native English speaker

the registration started with small talk about the position of the recorder and the computer

Zoé Crine: so, thank you very much for setting to...having us here with you...so...as you, probably had a look to our interview grid, we have a first general questions to begin, just to introduce yourself, in terms of professional background, who you are, very broad, as a beginning...

Kateljne Declerck: oh...my God...it is a long history, a long CV because I am older, so I will not give you the whole thing, you can look it up, but, I have been...I am almost retiring so I had my career behind me, but I have been a judge since 1993 first in the *Commission permanente de recours des réfugiés*, the old Court yeah (ZC: the old) and now in this one since the beginning, yeah, since 2005 before that, I worked for UNHCR actually for 13 years and I was a bit all over and I have been working in different continents and and I have been the president of the International Association for Refugee and Migration Law Judges...I was a member of this organisation, being the European President and then Vice President and then the world President from 2014 till Sept...February this year, when we had a new Ppresident who is a Kenyan judge...a judge from Kenya, so...I have done a lots ahahah, lots and lots ahahah...teaching and lecturing teaching of whatever you...everywhere in the world...

ZC: our second question is still very general and it was to define vulnerability according to you and maybe you can distinguish between, like, global...general definition, I would say, and a more legal one...

KD: yeah...I read your questions and I found it very difficult that you always talk about notion, and especially at the last question the notion will come to that, but I found that a difficult question, in the sense that, there is no notion and there is no definition of vulnerability in the Qualification Directive or the Procedures Directive there is no...nor did the Luxembourg court in any judgement on these Directives defined the notion of vulnerability either...I think it's it's quite...you have groups that are named in it...you have just you have jurisprudence of Luxembourg, but then in the Return directive...but ehm...it is...yeah...it is a notion that is used

and abused all the time that I can tell you for sure, every petition of a lawyer comes with another definition almost which is in a way understandable because it's something very personal, but on the other hand, it is something like a “moving object” and it shoot [word not clear 04.41], so it's...we all know what certain vulnerabilities are for sure...which are obvious ones, but these are not the difficult ones, the ones that are difficult are the ones that you cannot pinpoint, so when you say what is a notion of vulnerability? I can't give you that, because...yes I can give you all the different groups that you can find...I think that it's a later one of your questions as well...the elderly, the young minors, according to age or gender or whatever, disabilities and all that sort of things, but that's not that's not a def...a notion of vulnerability...that's just one of the groups of persons that might be vulnerable or might not be, but there are probably more reasons to think that there are that they are not...if you find somebody in front of you, who is blind and deaf and then...that is for sure that's a vulnerable person but does not mean that you can define vulnerability as somebody who is blind and deaf different so, I am sorry, I am making things complicated (ZC: no no, it is interesting) but this is to me very very worrisome, very often and as I say...ehm...the thing is that as we don't have anything of that kind in the Qualification directive and in the Procedures directive, then you can go to, you know, other European instruments, which of course do have some notion of that, like the European Charter of Fundamental Rights and they...ehm...and then there are, of course, a lot of international law that also defines certain categories of people that they consider vulnerable so I think that is where the legal concept then comes in and I think that for sure we can...when it's primary European law the problem does not pose itself in the sense that we can, of course, refer...I am sure...to that...but as such a notion in the asylum law, in the Qualification directive and in the Procedures directive, there is no such a notion

ZC: I just wanted to point out something, you mentioned that this kind of definition was used and – definition, I am quoting – was used and abused by people. What do you mean by used and abused?

KD: because...ehm...almost everyone who will come – I mean almost...not all of them – will say “this is my client, this person is vulnerable” for one reason or another, but the thing is that life is vulnerable and everybody has its things...I am not saying that the lawyers are necessarily wrong in saying so, it is just that that that is not what we look for. I can believe that you maybe you didn't sleep well last night because yesterday you have, I don't know, you saw an accident, then you're completely taken off garden [words not clear 08.11-12] and you don't know what happened then, and so on and so then today, you have to come in Court that you still a bit [sound of someone without breath, she meant that you are still shocked] for sure, that is true...and it doesn't mean that you vulnerable and on that spot? Well it certainly means that there is something not right for that moment, but does it mean that necessarily this impacts your whole asylum procedure, that's another question. It could, but it could not.

Francesca Raimondo: may I intervene? (ZC and KD: yes, of courseahaha), do you think that a definition of vulnerability would help in that sense?

KD: no because we have a lot of a law, primarily law...ehm...there is non-discrimination...there are so many things in our primary law that makes us makes it possible for judges to ehm...respect that notion of vulnerability – I am using now the notion that I said I shouldn't use, but you understand what I mean – and I think that if you name something, you put boundaries to it and... I do not believe that you can do that and I certainly would not like that, as a judge, in the sense that it would limit me to my possibilities, and life is too complicated, vulnerability is too complicated, there are too many sides of that... a person might not be vulnerable at one point, but he may be two months later and so it's...you have to have the possibility to ehm...take into account what is happening at that time before you, and why it is like that...and if you define something that you exclude things and so I would not want that, no, especially not with vulnerability, you can do that much more easily for other things, eh, you could for instance identify a group of people who say...okay the blind people and that's it and you make a boundary on that, you have to be 100% blind or 80% blind and then you come into that category, that is fine, but even so, I mean...ehm...this is a notion that should stay open because it's something that is evolving with medicine with our knowledge of medicine, with – not medicine as a whole – but with medication. Sometimes we don't know the effects of some certain medications for the moment, but maybe in five years from now we will know that and you'll see other results. So why limit it, why, why, why put a lid on the notion that this by definition in my view something that you cannot always...ehm...identify very clearly, at one point...

ZC: so you had mentioned several times that that was very not a notion so, but a very complex things and concretely, as the judge, basically how do you do when you have to identify vulnerability? Because it is not defined, it is very complex, it is broad, you do not want to put boundaries on that...how do you concretely do? If you do, I mean...

KD: well, yes, you do...but first of all, you have...we are not...it is...I would always, I always say and I repeat, it is for a judge hearing in the Court, on the one hand, you are the last resort, and it's more difficult because everything is grey here, things who are shining they pose no problem and so we don't even see this case, we only see what is bad and what is grey so so in the sense people have looked at that before us, you have had people from here in Belgium: the Alien Office, you have the Commissioner General and they already have looked at that, they have seen that something is wrong and they normally...they should have acted on it and I think in most cases they have...almost all cases I think they have, but there are things that can happen in between, a person is not a machine, so it might be the he comes in the first six months he is living on his adrenaline and then he falls in a hole after six months and he comes to the court. So, then things might be different, and so...but you have already his declarations, you have a whole file and if it's I always think, that's just me, that the better you prepare your cases, the more you will see, some people think that maybe we should just listen first to the person and be less...that might be true, I don't know, but it is just, I don't work that way...I need a former ground under

my feet so I need to know exactly who was in front of me, so I can understand why he says certain things or she says things and why not, and so I think that when you, you know, when people come to the court – I have seen thousands and thousands and thousands of cases and it is, of course, different from young judge who is just starting ehm...I've done interviews all around the world, I worked for refugee since the 70s, you were not even born then – but so it's different it's different and I am not saying that I can see that, that would be very wrong to say, but it is something like...ehm...sometimes, you know there is something, but it has nothing to do with the asylum procedure and and in what...that for me it is difficult...how does that impact? That, you know, the stories is very...let's say...very clearly bad...somebody who says...I am, I don't know, I am from Venezuela, and in fact he is from Angola, something very obviously impossible, but you still see that that person has something wrong and so, of course, it doesn't impact clearly on your decision, but impacts on how you write your decision at that time and...I think that is something that is difficult because you don't always know but...ehm...I see...ehm...I feel almost...and I get things out that even the lawyer would say “oh God, I didn't know that” and then the truth comes out and it's good because then people, even if they are refused, at least, they know that we know, which is good for them, I think, psychologically. It's...when I see clearly see vulnerability... ehm...in the Court, well, it depends, for instance, if somebody has a speech disability, that that's easy, we have all the time to give them...and...I just give them a little bit of water and that's it, you just try to be very relaxed and asking little questions...with small answers, yes/no, and then, make it a bit bigger as they are more comfortable...ehm...something like that so these are, I would say, the easy cases, in the sense that you can clearly, as a judge, do something about that, easily, the more difficulties when you don't...ehm...when there is not a physical disability, but a mental disability...that's more difficult.

The physical ones they can sit down they can...we have all this situations in the Court that we can easily do in their chairs, people can sit down, women who are pregnant, they can sit down...we have all these possibilities of taking care of the people when they come to the Court so...in that sense, I will not even call that necessarily a disability in the sense of the asylum procedure, but the disability in the sense of that person's life.

It is not because he is unable to walk, definitely he is a disabled person, but that does not necessarily mean that his mind is not (word not clear 17.55) that he cannot follow the asylum procedure correctly, so these are two different things, also. But it doesn't mean that you have to take that into account and make themselves comfortable when they are at the Court [I think she wanted to say that the physical problems need to be taken into account when the person is in Court] but, as I said, these are easy things to do, to take into account, let's say, the physical problems that a person has...and forem (word not clear 18.20) I think the most difficult ones that I see are probably people who are...ehm...I don't know this word in English ...ehm...no I know...stammering...these are then...that's difficult because they are nervous – of course they are nervous! – and so that that really usually I stop and I say, you know, to sit down and when everybody's gone, I will take your case at the end so nobody is in the Court room except them. So these are little tricks that you can do which just makes it more comfortable for them, they feel not so exposed that it's easy to do. I think probably all judges, do something like that, I suppose...

ZC: if you noticed some vulnerability can it like have any impact during the hearing, for instance, if you notice, because you are just noticing it because you read something and you are saying “oh, this person looks very vulnerable and there is like a documents attesting, justifying that he or she is very like have any impact during the hearing, (KD: yeah, yeah, of course)... which kind of?

KD: the way you approach them, the way you talk to them the way you ask questions or not ask question, so it's not...you know...the idea in a courtroom is not that you make people cry eh, not to make things difficult for them. On the other hand, I think very much that a person needs also to be able to explain what he has and have an answer to that and I think if you if you ehm..., just as a judge, like somebody says “okay, I know you nervous or, for instance, I know that you have that speech disability, for instance, but it's all right, we have time, don't worry about it”, of course that doesn't mean that he will be less nervous but, at least, he knows it's all right and I think in that sense, yes, it can help...does it matter how I...yes I think I will ask other questions – not other questions – I will ask my questions simpler, more simply to come to the same...because this is...the idea here is not that we start over, we have a whole file so we know what questions we need to put and I have very specific questions and...then...sometimes I will not ask certain things because I think “well, okay that's very clear that it is like that, so I will not go back on that door”. For instance, something...I will not...if somebody has been tortured I will not certainly going in and say “tell me about your torture”, I mean (ZC: obviously)...yeah okay but that impacts what I ask on...(ZC: yeah, of course) and if he has then his medical certificate to to...ehm ... normally we don't see this cases...but if he has medical certificate then I usually say “yes I have seen that you have been in prison and I have read all about it”...I will tell him that, so it's not like he has to doubt when he goes outside that I don't know it and I think it's important for people to understand that when you make a decision that you have looked at that as well – of course it will be in your in your decision – but I think for the person, If he comes or she comes to the Court because he is not obliged to if they come, they need to hear something but that's...but it does impact, of course, it does impact you, you adapt yourself every time to the new person, whether vulnerable or not, frankly

ZC: you're talking about, like, I would say way of adapting to people, whether they are vulnerable or not...there are also very specific and, I would say, limited vulnerability in time, for instance. Do you also adapt to this kind of vulnerability? For instance, I mentioned the case of hunger strike so people who are not vulnerable, I would say, *per se*, but who are vulnerable because they are putting themselves in a situation that renders them vulnerable, for instance. Can you imagine any adaptation to this kind of specific, I would say, vulnerability?

KD: ehm...other types of vulnerability in the sense of that hunger strike people, is that what you mean?

ZC: yeah, very limited on time.

KD: I think yes, probably, somebody who had an accident, somebody who had an operation, somebody who just gave birth two days before, you know, this is happening, these are things that happen so and they...ehm...of course, they are recovering from their operation, if it's a serious operation, yeah, it certainly impacts a person...so in that sense, yes, these are types of, let's say, ...yeah things that can happen, but is different from a hunger strike because a hunger strike is something that's that's...ehm...I remember those cases and it's been a long time now...but...all the Iranians on their **hunger strike (words not clear 24.58)** we had so many of them, but they didn't come...the thing is that, by the time they came, it was still at the *Commission permanente de recours des réfugiés* and so it was still different because by the time they came to us, you know, they were okay because they first had to go to the Commissioner general and then they took time to deal with these cases and, by the time they came to us, it was like three, four months later so...I don't really know – well probably there were some – who had already a negative decision and whose case were pending, but then I think in the cases of the of the commission...of the Iranians... the Minister had, at that time, had taken a decision that they could introduce a new application or something like that, if I remember correctly, so there was some other measures that were taken...but other types of temporary, perhaps there are, I will probably think about it when I go home this evening in the train...ahahah...but

ZC: I don't know if you like are used to be confronted with this type of limited, limited on time, vulnerability or not...

KD: well, as I said those who I just mentioned, yes, yes, we are confronted with that because people are here, they are ill and they have an operation, yes, of course, we have this, but then usually they don't...very often they don't come or sometimes they asked to postpone... but the lawyer can represent them in, if it's not necessarily, strictly necessary, to see them the...it depends on the case that or, as they come in a family, and one person of the family is having an operation or something like that...then the other person come, something like that...it depends...it depends...but it's never really...I never...I probably don't remember because I don't think it's a problem, usually it's okay...or if it's not okay then we postpone the session, I have done that a couple times because I wanted to ask certain questions and I know that a lawyer would not be able to answer them....and then I postpone... it doesn't happen very often but over the years it does...

ZC: I am checking where we...okay....we also wanted to approach the question of other factors that can impact the fact that we qualify someone as vulnerable or not and I put, for instance, the level of education, the socio-economic background of the applicant. Do they play a role in identifying vulnerabilities? And if we take the whole pictures can we say that sometimes we have compounded or multiple vulnerabilities because they have this kind of different factors interacting with each other?

KD: I think these are two different questions...when you talk about social social background, social, economical background and level of education, I don't know if this is really vulnerability, I would just say that this is part of that person, it is his being and, I have written very often already in my decisions, it is not because somebody has not studied that they're not smart, this is something completely different. I mean, otherwise, all forefathers, lots of them would be stupid that there were not because we are here...so it's, it's not it's not because you have university degree that you are smarter than somebody who has not studied and who is in front of me...it all depends on that person and, you know, you're probably know, the *the mama benz* – they called them – the women from Ghana and that area who are doing trading, they are called *benz* because of Mercedes-Benz...they're so rich and they go all over, but none of them know how to read and write...are they vulnerable? No, they are not vulnerable but they have something, yes, and they adapt to that it's not...It's like in our society, it is a problem not to know how to read and write, in other societies not as much because they have other ways of coping with that, of course, our world is getting more complex and...I'm just speaking generally, but so would I call that a person in front of me who doesn't read and write vulnerable? No, I would probably think, okay, this person does know how to read and write and I have to take that into account...

ZC: on the other sense, maybe, if a person in front of you has education, proper education does it impact the fact that he or she can be qualified as vulnerable? Because, for instance, in different cases, when women are like, I would say, have proper education, went through University and stuff and I read sometimes that judges say “yeah, but you have this kind of professional background, you have this kind of education level” and they insisted on that fact, so I don't know how it can impact, basically?

KD: yes, it can impact, of course everything...you have a whole person in front of you and every bit of that person is part of that person and this impact on your decision and if somebody has a higher education and pretends that he has been, for instance, very politically involved, then you can expect that person to be clear on that. And then, especially, if they say “okay, we had a leading role in whatever youth group or whatever” they need to be able to explain that...but it is not because you have a higher education in chemistry that you will be a good politician, so in that sense it all depends a little bit on what they say and what they pretend their profile is, not what you think necessary it is and I think that's why it's important to read what they say...if they say: “okay, I have done that, that and that”, yes you can, you can imagine that somebody who has been...ehm...in secondary education will be able to explain that correctly, somebody [with] higher education even more...but it...it depends, well...the thing is, if it's not, if it's an invented story, they definitely will fall through very easily if they have not had any **indication (not clear if the Judge says indication or education...32.44)** although not necessarily, you know, not necessarily if they are well prepared, but...it is not so that, because you have a higher education that you do better in your interviews in the Commissioner general, that is not the case, and I have seen that over and over again. It doesn't matter when you take into account what he should know because he says he knows...that that impacts but if he doesn't say that he knows that, for

instance, they say “I have never really been interested in politics”, but all of a sudden I was in the middle of something riot and they pick me up because I went to the dormitories in my University and I was in the wrong place at the wrong time, it's possible, and he might had to flee because of that, but his higher education, not really, especially if he is doing chemistry, is not really going to help him so...that is why I say I don't really consider that as a vulnerability the fact that somebody is poor and something, it is just... for me it's part of that person, of his profile and does that impact on the decision? Yes, everything of that person impacts a decision...also the fact that he has...a very, very poor background, okay, then he probably doesn't know certain things, so you will not have been going on tourist trips around the world for something like that, so...ehm...this is important in the sense that you can then for instance accept that...well...he travelled, somebody help him with his travel, he can't really explain it, for instance, this is an example and then you say okay, yes, he doesn't read or write and he knows that a plane look like that – when you look at Brussels Airlines and they have this **ten tons (words not very clear 35.00)** or whatever – I mean he would be able to explain that, there is a drawing so that he would not necessarily know other thing, so it would matter then, you would just dismiss that saying okay this is not important because it doesn't...it's acceptable that you would not know you just put aside so it impacts in that sense...but that is really...that this part of the refugee status determination process...and that is, you know, when you talk about vulnerability then this is black-and-white, but there are so many situations in between where somebody has, maybe, he knows how to read and write, but you know, I always look at the signatures and you see that this person knows how to read and write...he wouldn't be able to write a book with that handwriting, something like that. So, this is not black-and-white...there is...most of it is in between, and they know certain things or they are poor, but not so poor, because finally they did come to Europe. We don't really have the very poor people here, they can't move, they don't have the possibility the very poor and illiterate, unless somebody brought them here. You can also accept if a person has not been travelling a lot or have only been living in his own neighbourhood that he will make mistakes along the way and that is what happens, I think, but even with people who are not poor, who have been, let's say, take an Ethiopian who does not live in Addis Ababa but somewhere else and...ehm...has never really, you know, has travelled to Addis Ababa maybe once or twice and then comes overland through Libya to Europe, you know, the chances that he has problems in Libya is pretty big, so in that sense, yeah, he will arrive and he will be vulnerable because he or she definitely has lived through some nasty things and the chances of that are very real, but this is the something different, this is not a vulnerability in this sense of the asylum claim it is not because of that vulnerability that they left, they are vulnerable and then they have to take that into account and there are now rules for that, you know, of course, the way they have to be interviewed and all this sort of things and that has to be done...but as such it doesn't mean that they left because of reasons of Convention reason, they left for other reasons, but on the way, a lot of these people have had very bad times...

ZC: and what about multiple vulnerabilities, then?

KD: wow, yeah, of course, a child who is disabled and elderly who is disabled and then (word not clear 38.22) you can be homosexual and minor... you can be...yes, of course, there are many many combinations possible, yeah, these are just the obvious ones, so, you can have...as I said, you can be can be a minor who has...has indeed been, you know, ...having had troubles in...come from Afghanistan, passed through Iraq and then...got in a difficult situation there and is totally troubled by the time he comes here...very possible, very likely, even.

ZC: all right, so, yeah, I wanted to have also your personal opinion and because you mention the vulnerabilities entrenched in Belgian law and European directives. Do you sometimes noticed notice other vulnerabilities that are not entrenched in law, but are very real and concrete in front of you and...

KD: there are so many of them in there already...you have caused (word not clear 39.49) ages, elderly or young, minors accompanied or not, you have disabilities, you have...ehm...yeah, of course, all the physical harm done to the person, in the sense or torture, rape or something like that...others...trafficking...I don't know...I think it's more a question of...at our level...it's more...we don't see this really...if a person has really been...so for instance...tortured or something like that... these are cases we shouldn't see and usually we don't... they have gotten a status by the time the came...they don't need to come into appeal... But, yeah, other categories I would say subcategories probably (ZC: for instance), for instance, I don't know, mental illnesses of some sort and...yeah...probably...pregnant women, but you also have just delivered a children, I don't know...I don't really see that for the moment, I think, as I said, there are a lot of vulnerabilities that you can't really name, you can be, for instance, physically something bad, but not really bad bad, that you need to be hospitalized, but you can have, also, a mental illness and it is very, very difficult sometimes because... yeah... ehm...I am thinking of the case that I just had two weeks ago, this lady...this lady was from Angola and she was...she has psychosis, a serious one, and it was not at all...that was not a question, it was accepted, that there was something very wrong...she had also been in Belgium, she had been in a psychiatric institution and out and in and out and in, because, of course, for foreigners the whole situation of being *coloche* (word not clear 42.54) is quite different than for people who have also a sojourn or Belgians or foreigners who have a regular stay here, but...Anyway, for this lady it was quite clear, she had her story very clearly from the beginning and she said...“that's it”...It didn't really add up to certain degree, but what has...but in that study...there were certainly things that were correct, for instance, she said that “at one point, I ended up in the street and I was raped and I and...ehm...then finally somebody – and she said her employer – but it probably was her family who took her from the street, probably because of her psychosis, that happens everywhere, she was lost and got lost literally and then was vulnerable on the streets and then something happened to her because she did have a child and so...she had two children actually...and then she says yes, these people persecuted me, yes, of course, rape is a crime and a crime past and was done to this lady, but that was about 10 years before she came to Belgium and in between, she said, she works for somebody...I thought, well, I don't know how you can do that, but anyway, she insisted that was

the case, and it is only when I looked at the medical certificates from the psychiatrists from Belgium that I noticed that in one of them, one sentence that said...the only thing I have is an old psychiatric report from Angola from 2012 and that was the time that she was actually, that she was saying, that she was on the street and probably picked her up and put her in psychiatric facility because she was so bad and then she was protected by her family who probably brought her to Belgium...and that's the story. The thing is, it's very difficult because you have a lady who...who...she says she is all right, but she is not all right, she says she can do her story and, probably, most of what she said was actually pretty pretty... was acceptable...and was very likely, the only thing that wasn't likely was this...the conditions that she said that she lived in, which were not really bad, you know, but not really acceptable neither, if you would be in a ... psychosis and so, in that sense, you can say is that vulnerability? Yes, absolutely is vulnerable and they do...they did at the Commissioner general they did question her, they interviewed her at different times, when she was not okay, they postpone that and they made her come back again, and so on. So they did all what was necessary that they needed to do and then she didn't come to the Court, she said she didn't need to come to the Court, the lawyer could do that and the lawyer did and so... These are things that come up, now how do you define that? As mental illness? Yes, but you still have to make a decision in the case, I cannot say "well I cannot make a decision because she..." it doesn't work...still have to make that decision and so that that's...and then you way (word not clear 46.46) things, but it's difficult because I couldn't see her and it bothered me that she didn't come, I always does bother me when people do not come, but here, of course, I've nothing to say she was probably not well enough and she...I didn't hold that against her in the least, but I think it would have been better if she could have come...for her...not necessarily for me, but for her... (ZC: because?) because I think they people...I think it's a matter of procedural justice...to put a big word on it. I think people can accept whatever decision you take...make if they feel that it is correct or that the basis of this is correct and they...they will probably not say it out loud, but they would accepted it better, even in her situation...

ZC: as you are talking about women, we would like to insist on a specific vulnerability, which is the one of gender and how is basically gender viewed in relation to vulnerability? What is the link between the two, according to you? I mean...

KD: I don't think women are vulnerable because they are women, no, I don't think that...most women that I see are really very...fine women who know what they want and they know why they're here, probably sometimes even better than men, because they know why they want to come, they feel that they can help their families better than anybody else, I think that it is something that a lot of women have, so most of them definitely are not at all vulnerable, but, there is a big "but" on that, it depends why they left, it depends what their stories is, it depends where they come from, it depends on their age, their religion, their social background and all these other external things that can make or not make them vulnerable and that, of course, this is for many reasons, they can be disabled, they can be...you know they can be many things...So, yeah, but saying that women are vulnerable because they are women: no (!) this is not my

experience at all. On the contrary, I found them usually very courageous, courageous and firm in what they say. But it depends on the story, of course, it depends why they come and so on, it's... also... it's not because they are...it's not because of what they say or how they say it... it is what this... when I read what they have said in the interview for the Commissioner general, you can see what for them is important, why they think certain things are important and others not, and it is not necessarily what is important that I think is important, but it is sometimes very strange and sometimes... – well, when they are young, of course, and minors is a different story altogether female minors depending on how they got here, you can only hope they come by plane to Brussels or Paris or somebody...somewhere nearby, but otherwise if they have to go overland...yeah...that's not good...

ZC: do you include other things than women, I would say, in the gender category?

KD: do I include other...?

ZC: other profiles than women in the gender category, within gender category...

KD: well minors, unaccompanied minors, all the categories that exist

ZC: in gender?

KD: in gender, yes...they be double, gender can...alone...It's maybe not, or can or cannot...depending...but it can be, yes they can be traumatized, they can have physical things they can have, yeah, they can be many things, they can be homosexual, they can be lesbian, they can be other things, they can have been tortured they can have been... I do know, you have all the other categories who come...who can come into the category of women and gender which makes them...that's why you were talking about the double categories... women: there are so many kinds of them...

Laura Cools: I think she was also talking about trans-gender and non-binary persons, within the category of gender, who are not just women...as form of gender...

ZC: yeah, for instance, when we mentioned the gender category...(KD: Yeah) at first time people refer to women, maybe there are other categories that can fit within (KD: yeah, I didn't understand that...), no no your answer was interesting anyway night, it is nice...we don't expect like "proper answer", that way or that way...it is up to you...

KD: gender can mean a lot of things, yes, of course and I said that women, how women, what have happened to them, or men whatever, it is, of course the obvious ones: the homosexual, the transgender... and all these, but these are so obvious for me that I think this is...this are clear categories, I think, these are not something...

ZC: yeah of course, but it is interesting to see whether people mention it or not, whether is okay for them or not?

KD: yeah, for me it is very obvious that I...ahahah (ZC: no worries, it is fine) and...it depends...I mean...some homosexuals or all lesbian people have no problems where they come from, others do, so it ...makes them special, in the sense that their profile is special. Is it necessarily vulnerable? Mmm...maybe, maybe not... I have seen many people who are generally homosexual, who actually have no problem, except at one point they have other problems...political problems or whatever problems, but not because of their homosexuality, but...of course that plays a role in the sense that their social environments will be very often, depending on the country where they come from, limited or they will...ehm...they will be accepted or not. That all depends on the social and the other factors, the background factors, the socio-economic factors, the cultural factors, the religious factors that play a role in that sense...and that...that will have to be assessed.

ZC: another big type, I would say, of vulnerability you mentioned is age. So you are referring to minors and also to elderly? How are these categories connected to vulnerability, according to you?

KD: for the minors, I think that it is obvious and if they are unaccompanied minors...although, you know, the number of times I have to tell them “Okay, tell me the truth, because this is...you can tell that in school, but not to me because I don't believe it, tell me the truth”, and then they wake up...and then I start saying “take off your cap, take your hands out of your pockets and stand up straight”, that’s what I tell them...ahah. Then, they stand straight and then they start and ...you can see that they start thinking... it's like they need a little bit of a push, especially when there are an adolescent. They're not different from any other adolescent [it is possible to hear from her voice that she intends that adolescents are always a group that is a little bit problematic] that they want to go through life...and so on...you need to say “this is serious now, you think” or when they blabla [the judge intends when they do empty talks] I say “no no, stop, think twice, then you speak”...things like, you know, you treat them like an adolescent, and you don't expect them to be a grown-up. And you know that they will say foolish things, but you can tell them that it is foolish, they understand enough, but there are of course minors that they do...I mean, it is not one thing, there is not one answer, there is not one profile, everybody is so different and so you have to adapt yourself constantly as the judge to the vulnerability of that age. A 12 year old is not the same as a 16 year old and even if there are 20, in my view, they are still children, you know, at 20 people still do stupid things. At 40, normally they shouldn't but, you know, it all depends on how they grew up, where they grew up, what happened in between, if they have been...if they left their home, let's say, at 16 with an older brother and came overland through Turkey and Greece, and so on, to Belgium and they missed out on two years of their lives and then they come here and there are not minors, they are 19 years old, perhaps...that's not

the same as a normal minor who grows up in a stable environment so they have that vulnerability that I cannot name because there is nothing to it, but that...this makes them different...that makes them different, that makes them...that you need to take that into account and that whatever they say, you need to think that yes, maybe he does want to exaggerate because...or otherwise they might, you know, be...a differently...they might not want to speak, it depends, it depends on the character of that person...because that plays a big role as well. We never mention that, it's never mentioned anywhere but I think the character, really, of a person is...it is very very important...that is why you make friends or not, that is why you will go to one person and say certain things and not to the other person, but that's the same thing for the people in front of us...somebody might be just, you know, yeah... I can tell you so many cases that I have in my head that go around there... to illustrate that, but it's so true, so true, that makes such a big difference...

ZC: all right and about the older people?

KD: perhaps because I am old, it's very funny, it is very often, very often...we have somebody...ahahah... and they say: "my mother is old" and then is 15 years younger than I am and then the lawyers are always [the judge makes us understand that the lawyers are somehow embarrassed] saying "in their countries is a bit different", so they try to excuse their clients...ahahah

Anyway, I think that elderly...it depends. Generally, I don't think that plays a big role, because elderly people are usually... they have more experience in life, they have more experience with life, they have... they understand things better, they have been able to learn and know what's going on, what the evolutions in the countries is...If you take an old person from Iraq, he will remember, you know, Saddam Hussain and than...all the things and... so he will be more knowledgeable very often and I think if I have elderly people in front of me, then I usually take that into account and I tell them and I say "you must remember that"...yes, okay... But then again, there are certain things that we are... It all depends again on the socio-economic, cultural, religious background, where elderly people live with their children and you separate them from their children...that is a problem, and this is something that, of course, this is not the asylum procedure, it is not part of that, it is family reunification and things like that...but, in certain cases, it could be...in certain cases, it could be... for instance, it's not my case, but there is a case from a colleague of mine, here in front of me, who an Iraqi...who the whole family was in Belgium, has been recognised as a refugees, and he was behind, the elderly men, because he is disabled, he wasn't able to come because of his disability and the situation in Baghdad at that time had been...had improved and, normally, we would not accept people from Baghdad, but in this case that was put in the balance.

ZC: because he was old and disabled?

KD: he was old and disabled and dependent totally for his care to the family he used to live with and because they did, they did not get subsidiary protection. They got refugee status, so there was a clear link of persecution there...and that he has been in that sense he had...ehm...he said, and it was accepted, that by the Commissioner general that this might impact on him, but they considered that it was not so important, as to have to...to give him any status...and here, in the Chamber, they decided differently.

I remember a case of a woman who was...it was a long time ago...Somali woman who, her children, her daughter...she was from somewhere outside Kismayo... from a smaller town out...somewhere there, so not from the capital...and she...they were bombed in the village and everything was in flame and she was very very badly burnt and so badly that she – in those places you don't get good care – sun is burning so you don't want to go outside when you're so badly burnt and so she stayed in the house for six/seven months, I mean in the hut house for six/seven months but that in the meantime, her daughter had fled to Belgium and had received refugee status, and then it was decided by Commissioner that, indeed, yes, the things were very bad, but in the meantime, things were a bit better and, anyway, she had been able to stay there for that long and she was not harmed, she was not persecuted and I thought that was not not fair. I thought that was not correct in the sense that...the situation in Somalia had not fundamentally changed, and that was one of the main reasons, but the fact that she was elderly and inside – because she couldn't even go outside because she was so badly burnt – it could not be held against her, the fact that she was elderly – because she was like 70 years old or something, she was really an older lady – and she was totally dependent and she had her neighbours and whatever **clan (the word is not clear 01.04.56)** who came and help her, but I...she was not...I didn't give her refugee status because she was elderly or because she was recuperating from a terrible, terrible disease...I mean accident accident...I mean bombing...I don't know what you can call that...an accident, but anyway...it is...so for me, these were important factors as well, and so... you say “how does it impact?” I cannot tell you every time how it impacts, but it does impact, of course, you cannot say this is a normal way of living, or that she has been hiding, she was just unable to go outside so...they are many things like that will always intervene...the fact that she was a woman, the fact the she came from Somalia, the fact, you know, as I said, there are so many factors who always come, it is not one thing – sometime, I mean, perhaps – in the Court I think it is rare that you can really say “only because she was a woman and elderly”, NO...I mean... it is...yeah...ehm...

FR: may I intervene?

ZC: yeah, go for it, Francesca

FR: you said that there are many factors that have an impact and, especially with regard to minors, do you think that culture have an impact on their vulnerability as minors, any...in Western countries, at 20 people could still do stupid things, as you said, but maybe in other culture they are considered adult...how do you evaluate this? If you do...

KD: I think you have to evaluate where...it is very difficult...okay...let me repeat. When I said you can do foolish things, I think that what I mean is that, during asylum procedures, if they do foolish things or they say stupid things because of their age, that's what I mean, that you cannot take that against them, that you have to understand that they are just youngsters who, you know, who are not grown up and they...this is different from what you're saying...what you're saying is, depending on the country and the culture they come from, at 16 they are not supposed to do any foolish things because they have full responsibility, perhaps for part of the income of the family and the care of that family, and that, of course, they have to live up to that.

I think if we...if it impacts, it's probably the other way around, it's probably because very much we consider that they...ehm...how should I explain that...a lot of the times when I see decisions or judgements I see that the postpone...[the judge corrected herself] they transfer that our time and age and place and I think that is not correct. You have to much...more look at what is expected of them over there and...ehm...and if they have to be grown-up, yes they have to be grown up... that's how it is and how it was here, also, yeah, you know, during the war in Europe, you better grow up quickly, so it's the same thing everywhere, except that for now, we have, you know – who knows how things will evolve even in our part of the world – but that we can be more lax with them, we can be more free with the youngsters, they can do more things, but in most of the world, it is not like that and even in...ehm...I'm not saying necessarily in places where they have...a war or something like that...I think Chinese child or a Japanese child better grow up quickly and study seriously when they are 14 years old, cannot permit themselves to do what they do in most of the schools and they are not persecuted, they just... it's their culture that tells them...for perhaps us...are too strict or something like that, but that's the way it is and I think that is how you have to see it. Of course, it depends on what and what type of expectations there are, there are certain things where we could say “okay, that's not reasonable at all”, perhaps, you know, cultural things that should... ehm...how should I say...what example could I give...even a sanction for having not done something it is so severe that it really harms the youngster, then, of course, that is not acceptable. So it all depends on how you...but that is really difficult because you're weighting their cultural habits against yours and you think that we are always right, and that we are always...there is so much racism I say in the asylum world, it's incredible, it upsets me sometimes to read what I read...then I say “please!”, I mean, it is like people in Africa are all barbarians, that is so bad sometimes, really bad... and a lot of asylum seekers play that role, “yes, to us in Africa we say this and that”, come on!, every parent anywhere in the world wants their children to grow up, I have grand-children, so there won't...but there can be certain things that go too far, but that's sometimes legislations that's probably...you know, at one time, I remember, but that's also long time ago now, during the 80s, when Khomeini was just in power in Iran and where they had, they use this *sharia*, they cut their hands when somebody stole something... yeah well...that's not really acceptable as a punishment, is it? So, you know, it depends how far you go and how...and what you say but, definitely, I think it is wrong always to see things from our side, not wrong, I mean, I should not use that word, it's not wrong...ehm... it's... you have to be careful, let me put it in that way, you

have to be careful to look at things from a Western point of view and think that is always the best for that situation in that country who has another culture and another religion...something like that, that's what I mean...but there's very little information on that very often, how...ehm...the number of reports about...let's say... sociology and cultural reports on what happens in villages to women. Have you seen many of those? I haven't. We don't get this anthropological (ZC: insight) insight in situations because that goes along with that...what is acceptable and what is not, and then you have to know what is acceptable in that country. And so...yeah...that it's not easy, so the because it's not easy, that's usually why most asylum instances and decision-makers fall back on what they know, which is your own culture, that is the easiest to compare it...

ZC: Francesca, do you want to add something?

FR: no, it is fine for me, thank you

ZC: all right, I have another question on specific vulnerable person. I know you're not very confronted to victims of human trafficking (KD: no) no, I know, but I wanted to know, as a judge, what's your opinion on...I mean...which could be difficulties for people victims of human trafficking to get international protection? What's your opinion on that...how it is difficult for them...

KD: you know, in Belgium we have another status for that and they do not even come to our procedure, they go **immediately (word not clear 01.14.00)** to the other procedure so we don't see that and, sometimes, I think that is not a good thing either, in the sense that, when somebody is genuinely persecuted, I think, the recognition of that in the form of refugee status, is probably very important to that person but, on the other hand, in the beginning I felt very strongly about that, when we had these all story, long time ago now...but now perhaps having seen...things...how things work, it's probably...ehm... it's not the procedure itself... it's all the rest with that...the way they are taken care off in Belgium, how they are treated, how they are...the whole package, I would say, is probably quite, quite okay...ehm...and the fact that then they cannot be recognised as a refugee, even if there are...perhaps that's just the result of that, but I still think that this...ehm...perhaps they can live with that, I don't know. But it's my experience that somebody who has been really persecuted wants to be recognised for that, it's something that's part of that person. It's very, very important thing in his life or her life.

But so, once we see trafficking or the expulsion cases, or either when we do the urgent appeals procedures or sometimes when, you know, when they are in the airport just going to be sent back...returned...that they still quickly ask an asylum procedure...an asylum, as they normally shouldn't have...didn't do it, but this are mainly prostitutions, Nigerian women, that the... but they won't talk, I tried very often, so...“tell me that is not what you did here, you were picked up on that street, we know that, we have that report indicating...” an even younger ones, you think, beautiful young girls...it's a waste, and they do not talk, they don't...so it's another procedure it's another set of mind, probably from those who really traffic knowingly and then who are

trafficked because along the way, there were picked up and trafficked or because along the way they were trafficked or smuggled, these are two different things, of course, you know...but, I think, some of them... aren't...ehm...didn't...just just...yeah...I can imagine that when going through the Sahara, a lot of bad things happen to people...sometimes they talk about it, sometimes they don't...ehm...if they are really trafficked, then they are usually picked up. I cannot really say that a lot of people definitely came overland, but a lot of more, probably didn't and they say they did...but...I don't know if we have so many traffic cases in that...I mean...it is not part of...normally, it should be in the file and if it's not in the file are, normally, there are not, normally, I don't know...

ZC: we have also seen that vulnerability is not only a matter of law it is also a matter of politics and then, the notion, I know that you don't like the word, but vulnerability also appears in political speeches (KD: of course, very easy, eh) and, so, for instance, we have seen a speech from the Theo Francken, who said “yes, we want to protect the vulnerable we want to limit the abuses” and I think that’s interesting because you mentioned, also in your speech, that there is abuses around vulnerability, so I wanted to have your view on that...which...(KD: my view is not the same as Francken, for sure, but ahahah), your personal view is what matters...(KD: yeah...hope so...yeah), I just took the example because it is very striking, you just listen to politicians speaking about asylum policies and you will hear repeatedly vulnerables and vulnerabilities and “we want to protect the vulnerable” and “vulnerable first” and stuff.

KD: no, you protect those who are in need of protection...entitled to protection, not because they are vulnerable, if they are vulnerable, okay, but that's not why you...its it's this sort of thing...you know... it's cheap thing that we have to give a little present to those who can...I mean...it is like...this old, I am sorry to say, this old Catholic thing, you need to do some good for the poor children then you go to heaven, but it is not what asylum is...asylum is...and protection is not something we give, it something that people earn, not earn, but are entitled to – that’s the right word – because of what had happened and it's not, it's not a gift. It's not wanting to help the vulnerable, that has nothing to do with it. They can do that in another procedure, if they want to give an humanitarian status to certain people because they feel that they...okay...ehm...so much the better. But that is not what we're talking about here, now...no, not at all. I think this is...and it shouldn't, it should really not because everything is become so political and everything is mixed up, and it's like...we are the good guys, who just can hand up certificates...this is really very bad, because if people start looking at it that way the ... (word not clear 01.21.05) starts to look negatively at people who are...who receive... refugee status, international protection status, they shouldn't look at these people that way and say “these are all vulnerable”, my God, they are not all vulnerable, some people have probably more, many under banks (word not clear 01.21.28), that we altogether will ever have, they are very rich and they have a life very richly, a lot of them. A lot of people that we see from Venezuela, they are not poor people, they are very rich people, others are less rich, but definitely some of them are very... and have been living very, very well, but just, you know, because of the situation, they think maybe we should make sure that we have

an outcome somewhere, and they arrange themselves in that way where... not necessarily get the refugee status or the protection status...but I'm just saying refugees are not necessarily poor, illiterate, handicapped people, most of them are not and they have to be **quiet/quite (not sure about the word)**, I mean, and that is probably one of the sad things about that, that the most people we see here are an asset to their own country and they leave, which is bad for the country for their country, and that is... but that's another story, I mean, that is not what we do here, but it is... **(word not clear 01.22.38)** what I mean by abuse is that, for sure you all know that, people... a lot of Africans think that if they can say they are homosexual that they get more easily refugee status, or they have been converted or they have been, you know, from Iran, you know all these things, these, yes, definitely, these are abuses, that's what I mean, but...okay...they

ZC: is there any specific categories really prone to abuses? Do you see any?

KD: oh, you know abuse...

ZC: you can call it like abuse or maybe you see it as a strategy, also, from their side...

KD: well it is a strategy, it is a strategy to come and be able to migrate because they found another way to do it, so yeah... is that bad? It is ... **word not clear 01.23.38**, of course, to lie...so be it. But a lot of a lot of people from Sudan come for medical reasons and a lot of them are members of the medical profession, are themselves doctors, dentist and so on. A lot of people from Armenia come from kidney dialysis, a lot. A lot of people come from for medical care. I had a case...scary...not scary, but I was quite taken aback... but somebody in my courtroom had an heart attack and fell and so we called the ambulance and, of course, immediately they asked "can..." – he was not bad bad, but, you know he was bad – and they said "had you had any precedents" and he says "yes, I came here several years ago, I had a heart transplantation in Brugmann University Hospital" and, of course, he didn't say that in his asylum procedure and I was not supposed to hear that because that was medical but it just happened in front of me in my courtroom so I heard it. Of course, I did not use it against him, but it's clear that this is abuse. He came, he was treated one time, he had come again, he learned that if you are in asylum procedure, you get medical care. It is definitely, it's abuse of the procedure, yeah, but there are many people who come for medical reasons. Yes, definitely. Also Belgium is very well known for people who have problems in getting children. So a lot of people from the Middle East, particularly...

LC: which grounds are they coming to? On which grounds?

KD: they invent a story (LC: oh they invent, they cannot say just...) no, no they do not say that. They just on the sideline...on the sideline...[everybody chats in the room and then some small laughs ahahah]...I read those files, I see what...I have been there, I have in that...mmm mmm that's there. I find that out because I look at it and I realise that, but most of my colleagues will

not even look at that at because they don't or they won't...because it's not important for the story. You cannot use that in the story...

FR: why?

KD: because unless they say it explicitly, it is a medical matter and I am not supposed to expose medical matters, also, because it won't help me in my decision making, they probably will say anyway that "no, no, no we ask that, it is maybe be true, but still the other is also true". So it doesn't help you anyway...except for certain types of... I think if I have written down once or twice in a judgement, it is a lot. Most of the time I just leave it like that, but I will talk about in my Courtroom, and that's why I think it's important for people to be there. I will not put that in my decision, but I will talk about it in the Courtroom and say "okay, you came for that". That's it. say more than that, but they know, and I think it's important that they know that I know and so I don't say more than that, but they know. And I think it is important that they know that I know. And so they know why I made my other decision in the way I have made. But a lot of... not a lot of, but there are not a lot of that we know...but, especially at one time, it seems to have changed now, perhaps people can come more easily now with medical certificate and go to the hospital than before. Maybe that's the reason, I don't know. But for these fertility things that definitely is...ehm... now rare, but it was, let's say in the times of the Appeal Commission, it was...that was...it happened quite a number of times and almost always from that area.

But then for medical care, yes, that's definitely... and sometimes they don't even hide it, I mean, they...a lot of times...they have serious diseases, they have...I mean, it is not minors things, they don't come for a little something, these are people who really come for serious medical care or for their children. Okay, I'm not going to say you cannot be a good parent, so just to keep that out of it and do...you deal with what you have. But you know that is the reason why and they know you know.

But this is a vulnerability? Of course, what is...certainly a vulnerability of their parents when they stand in front of you with totally disabled child and they say, you know, here, we can get care for him or her...I am not being the one who throw stones at them, but I am taking that into account, yeah, in one way or another...because that's another, that's another vulnerability that you can never define in anything...vulnerability is a scary part for the parents who wants to come because their child is still seriously ill, that he will die in his own country...

ZC: talking about political speech and, generally, Belgium asylum policies, we can see that there is this kind of security framework around migration policy which is coming, years after years... Does this kind of security approach live room for vulnerability according to you? And in which sense. Or does it conflict with vulnerability? Because we cannot see how it works together...

KD: it depends...ehm...it is...I would say...generally speaking...I don't think somebody will be denied international protection because of a security and also it depends on the securities...there are some really...decisions that are taking...ehm...stealing an apple when you're hungry is not a

security reason, if you steal ten times an apple then you have ten (... words not clear 1.30.51)...and so on, it still isn't a public order case, of course, terrorism is another matter and that will impact for sure...ehm...but... if you have committed murders, definitely it is going to impact, but it impacts in different ways, it impacts not only because we get a report that...or because the Commissioner general says that it's a matter of public order, it will impact because we will taken along as one of the elements that, in your assessment of the case, you will start to say, okay, this is not the person who pretends he is, he is somebody else and then that might lead to squashing the decision, sending it back saying "look at that again" or else if it's very serious and yeah... then it certainly can impact, but then because you start doubting everything and...ehm... then again it for me, I have had many cases like that, I must say, so I'm not so...it's more in the withdrawal of refugee status that we have had to deal with that more, not when granting protection. I don't really recall any of those. Yes, of course, sometimes there is something in the file, like, somebody stole something, but it is okay, but it doesn't really... if it is something, I am not saying this is good to steal, not at all, but it is something that you can weigh, I mean if somebody steals because he's hungry... if he wants to shave himself and he steals shaving soap...okay...it is not good, but it's not going to impact on my decision but I don't really... I think it's in the withdrawal always of refugee status when we get this public order and national security matters and that is always something we look at very carefully any of the judges of the Chamber...I mean any of the judges of the Court, I think, I'm sure...they will do the same thing, you look at it very carefully, because you have to really assess – is that so serious? What was his case before? Why has he been granted a protection? Was that a subsidiary protection? Is the situation in that country now different? and so on –. When somebody, let's say, has tried to go back to Iraq and, of course, they don't go through the airport here but they always go to Bremen or one of the airports in Germany and then go from there to Iraq, but now the information is often a gift passed from one to another. Then...these are things that I do by the book in the sense that I really look at how...why he received refugee status? The thing is that...the difficulty is that the Commissioner general doesn't motivate his positive decisions. So, in principle, I don't even know why he received refugee status, I only have the decision, I only have their interview and I can more or less guess why they give somebody subsidiary protection, see if they come from Iraq, well, you more or less know...or why they give refugee status, but still I remember having refused one of those redraws (01.35.14) because... – what happened? I don't know remember now – he came from a certain area in Iraq and they gave him subsidiary – yes, this what it was – and they gave him subsidiary "C" of that and they said "he can go to Baghdad" and I said "no no, this is not correct". If you get subsidiarity "C" because he was from another part of the country, you cannot just now say "he can relocate himself somewhere else", then look at it seriously and so I said "no, this is wrong", so I looked at it in a procedural way, carefully, and say... – also, not only, but also in a procedural way – and then for the reasons why they consider it public order of...ehm...that is something that is... you have to look at it case by case...and it is to see how serious, indeed, it is... and if it serious and we all look at it very carefully because we refuse a lot of them... because we don't think this is really a reason to send somebody back or something...

ZC: okay, I have two questions left before we close this meeting...and I have a question concerning the judgement *MSS v Greece* from the ECHR and, just a simple thing, in this case-law the Court has said that asylum seekers were basically vulnerable *per se* and I wanted to have your opinion on this saying from the Court...

KD: oh, yeah yeah, I remember that, and I read that and I thought...okay, this is MSS...but you have also *Tarakhel v. Switzerland* and ... (word not clear 01.37.05) and you do not cite them, why not? Ahahah...if I can ask a question...ahahah

ZC: yeah why...here what is interesting to us is vulnerable *per se*, you know...

KD: because you are a refugee (ZC + KD: you are vulnerable *per se*) this...

ZC: that is why is interesting to us because we sometimes see others vulnerability which is not inherent to the person which are, basically, coming from the situation, from the administrative procedures, other types of vulnerability which basically are not inherent, so we wanted to have your opinion to say...

KD: could say that again? You sometimes see what...?

ZC: vulnerabilities that are not inherent to the person, for instance that come from situation or from the administrative situation of the person, you know...

KD: you mean like people being in Greece

ZC: or, for example, having no status...they are vulnerable, not because they are a women or disabled, but just because they have no status. This is another type of vulnerability, which is not biological, I would say, and so here the Court said "asylum seekers are vulnerable *per se*" like just the simple factor of being an asylum seekers is to be vulnerable, we just want to have your opinion on this *per se*, basically...

KD: yeah...anyway, there are two things, of course, that the Court has continued its jurisprudence and altered it and that the jurisprudence of the Luxembourg Court and of the Strasbourg Court are different, but I won't go into that because you're not asking me, but it is important because we are not talking about the same type of vulnerability, but...I would say any person, a Belgian who has not been regu(lar) [the judge stop herself in saying regular, she intended the Belgian begging, that will be clear later]...that in you can see them in the Nord Station who is begging and living on the street, is he vulnerable? Of course, they are and if you foreigner and you live in a country where you have no attachments and no...ehm... you cannot go anywhere, of course you are...you have three children, your...ehm...of course these people are vulnerable, but that's another thing, that's another thing because there are vulnerable because

they...you know...the people who want to go...ehm... the people who live in Calais or the ones that are in the Maximilian Park here or the ones who just a couple days ago, the five who are in their ... in the front of the ... words not clear 01.39.52/55 they save them from the sea...yeah... these people put themselves in terrible situations that they put themselves often in that situation, not always, but they put... a lot of times it's also because they don't know or they... you know, the people from Calais, you would say, if they really, really prosecuted in their country, why don't they ask refugee status or protection in France, why they *per se* have to go to Britain so, you know, I can't really say, you know, what I think about the *per se*, in the sense that, it is so different from one person to another...you can have certainly some people who fall between all the cracks or all the chairs and who just end up nowhere...and very often those people who have probably psychological problems or something like that and don't...or just listened to the wrong person, or do something with these people that they cannot help themselves and there are dumb [01.41.06]... not only vulnerable because they are...and they don't have status or anything like that...because they don't know how to manage their lives and that means that somebody should take care of that...in our countries at least, I think there should be social assistance or something like to help them out of that situation because, yeah, they are incapable of doing so or they have become incapable of doing so, that is also possible. People who are quite fine when they left their country... I remember very clearly a case...ehm...an Ethiopian man from Ogaden who was so badly hit on the head and in Libya that he became retarded and there was another group of Somali who travelled with them to Belgium, took them along and took care of him... until...they came to Belgium and they were...two of them were even in the Court when his case came up...and they said "yes, that's what happened". People like that need to... well he was lucky because this Somali young men took care of him...but, normally, people like are left like in streets and are unable to look...but then there is a vulnerability in them that means that definitely, in our world, somebody should take care of them and help them, and what whatever the reason may be...maybe it's better for them to go back to their own country where their parents are or something like that or not, but that has to be seen and taken, I mean that should be taken care of... it is the same thing for an unaccompanied minor often... they are sent by their parents, they do not come here by himself...but by the family, most of them. So they're extremely loyal to the parents, which is normal, and they will lie all around, and it's really sad because they are so vulnerable and they are so sad, there are so unhappy here that you think "this is not the solution for them", but that is not up to us to do, I can only see that, it is up to other services in the country to deal with that...

But I think also that in *MSS* also the fact was that the situation in Greece was definitely not the way it is supposed to be, it is still very very difficult, but still it depends if you're an asylum seeker or a recognised refugee or you have a status, but if you're an asylum seeker is still not easy...same in Italy, it's not always easy when you're still an asylum seeker, but if you have a status, okay then, it is still not easy, but it is still...ehm...you know, even in Belgium it is so difficult for people to make their lives and some of them know how to do that better than other and... but to say that all refugees are vulnerable, No! That's really not correct, to them, in particular, I don't think a lot of them would even like that to be said that they are vulnerable but

that they need help and that they need to be able to...that we owe to the Conventions that we signed and that we promise that we will respect that we respected that all the way and when there are asylum seekers that we take care of them and that we put them in shelters, and that we give them food, if necessary, and so on...yes, that is what we did when we signed up for all that, so we certainly should do that and that people who come to a new country or in a more difficult situations that the ones who have been living here, yes... and if there are small and unaccompanied or young families, you know, what you were saying, the social background is difficult, they don't know how to read and write and so on...that's why you have vulnerable groups in the first place in the asylum procedure and so you can actually have equality and justice... It's not there...they are not there because you need to give them something, no, they are there because you need equality in your procedures and they cannot have that equality unless you take care of them, unless you interview them specially, unless you give them more time to do certain things, unless it's...ehm...it's justice, it is not...it is not...they are not there, you know, so, out of the goodness of our hearts we can do something like that...

ZC: yeah, it is not a favour

KD: no, it is not at all a favour, it is justice, it's procedural justice, it is equality before justice, it's it's... it is the same thing with people who are disabled or something else...it's...so there is no discrimination between them and others, that's why you have these groups and that's why you have to treat them differently, not because you give them something, but because you wanted them be equal to the rest.

ZC: okay, just that last question before we go...

KD: oh, these questions on notions, I was stuck with that before I went to all the rest of your questions...ahahah...I said "what?!" ahahah

ZC: I will put it differently, so it is better... (KD: thank you...ahahah), I would just say like...is vulnerability, as currently put in law (KD: there is nothing in law)...the categories (KD: ah, the categories...all right) are entrenched in law...this is the vulnerability in law (KD: okay, okay)...this category approach, I would say... according to you, are these categories adapted to face vulnerabilities, I mean, in real life? Or...

KD: I think I have already answered that question, in the sense, yes, a lot of them are, definitely, and it's good to have certain categories in law and it's definitely, you know, after all the troubles from before...the CEAS, you know, when we still have to deal with the Convention alone and all the problems we had in Europe as a whole with...what to do with homosexuals...what to do with ... word not clear 01.48.22 what to do with minors what...and so on... this has now been defined and it's not only the fact that they are in a category, it is also the fact that there are procedure, obligations that come along with that...that is more important and because of that they

are treated more equal and are treated...I am not saying that in practice...you know, honestly, even before the CEAS we were doing the same thing... as a judge, at a time, I was doing exactly the same as I do now...except that now we have the law, which is better than before, and that it is clear, it is for probably, I don't know, for certain judges, or certain governments, or certain institutions that were still questioning is a homosexual...can that be reason for prosecution? This is out of the question, now...so, but I think I would have done the same thing before...I am sure I did the same thing before than I did now... but it is better to have in there, these categories as long as they are not limited, as long as it isn't something that...ehm...it is no... I think it's no coincidence that the Luxembourg Court has not really mentioned that, as such... except for the Return Directive... In their jurisprudence when it comes to the Qualification Directive... I think it's quite...perhaps they will...they are probably waiting for more cases and more jurisprudence, national jurisprudence, although they are not supposed to look at that and in principle they don't (ZC: it is important for them...) Well...I think the way you write a judgement, even when it goes to Luxembourg, means something...so, in that sense, they can take that along with them, but there are definitely more vulnerabilities than the ones of the categories, although the categories are big – I printed them out, actually, I though what categories? – (ZC: from the Directive or the Belgian law?) in the Directive, I look at the Directive [the judge leafed through the pages]: so single parents with minor children...but you know it's always different because you have the Reception Directive and you have the Qualification Directive and the vulnerabilities are not the same, it's not necessarily the same. It's not because you need, as a single mother with four teenage daughters, you will not put them together in a reception centre with nothing but male, with men around and that you need special situations for them...of course, you do... but does that make them vulnerable when they come to the asylum procedure? Not necessarily, not for that reason, at least...but for the reception, definitely, that will be the same... minors, yes, of course, it is always... pregnant woman, yes, you need to take care of them, that is what I said, you signed the Convention, we signed the obligations, we need to take care of these people, make sure that they have the best conditions that they can deliver the child in the best condition, and that they put the baby in the world, yeah, but that doesn't mean that here her brain is wrong or that she cannot answer the questions in the asylum procedure. No. So in that sense, yeah, other serious forms of violence on women and children, I have seen those, of course, and then the elderly person, of course, the Convention for the children.

I don't know if all these are not enough. I think it gives a serious indication of what they are looking for and that not every vulnerabilities is a vulnerability, in the sense of the refugee Convention, or prevents them from...ehm...following the...ehm...hurts their rights and inflicts on their rights as an asylum seeker...ehm... but, I don't know, you can always have ...there are certain categories that hand all the time to do vulnerable people...before people who are now considered the vulnerable, used not to be considered as vulnerable... especially mental diseases and things like that. People with one leg used to be considered okay, you travelled the world, and is probably still can in some cases, but in other cases, not at all...,you know, but all these things are... I don't know, it all depends and...I think it's what for me is most important is that you do not close the thing...that you leave it open and that you can take into account the vulnerability of

certain things...and I remember a case where a boy came with his mother from Sri Lanka where he had, definitely, he was not smart... and he was in the school bus and he had... – he was 16/17 years old or 18... he was already a major – well, he had looked at the girls a little bit too closely, and there were complaints and police reports and they said he was harassing girls on the bus. That's probably... he didn't touch them or anything like that... but they probably got scared of him, and anyway, this was all in the report and things like that. The thing is that he was just very, very, very low IQ and he behaved like... his hormones were too quick and he...things like that...I am not justifying it, but I mean that... when they are asking him questions on who is the president now, because there is a new president in Sri Lanka and things like that...I said no, I will take his interview only the questions that relate to him personally: how old he is – because he was more honest than his mother on how they came to Belgium, she said exactly the truth, because he is too stupid to lie, to say it in unelegant words – but that's all the rest, everything that has to do...is out of the debate I will not take that into consideration because he's not able to answer those questions because of his low IQ and that cannot be held against him. Now, how you will define here as a category? How low your IQ have to be to be low? (ZC: yeah, that is true)...so you cannot and, in that sense, there was enough in that file that I could read where I could certainly see that he was very, as I said, very correct, he was straightforward, very correct in his answers when it came to anything that had to do with his personal life, he was smart enough to say that, but anything that was a made up story by his mother, he couldn't because he didn't live...that I wasn't going to go to hold that against her...I mean both those were refused, but I was...would be not really correct, wouldn't it?

FR: may I ask something? (KD + ZC: yes, go for it Francesca) I found very interesting that you said that you didn't really change your way of working from the past, that you were doing almost the same...so how do you...why do you think then that the vulnerability discourse became so frequent in the last decades? And, if you find this definition not that useful, because it is important to look at the story itself because each story is different, would you think that would be useful to give another definition or another notion, maybe precarity and so on, these are two different questions, but they are somehow connected...

KD: yeah... I think that when you look at the categories that they are in there, they did not fall out of the sky, these are the categories where all the countries who are, you know, when the Commission drew up the Directives and later were put into Belgian law and implemented in any of the member states... it's not like they were all of a sudden brave “oh, we are going to do something for that...” it is they put down the situation as it is. They knew that, of course, the minors had to be taken care of, that...if they are unaccompanied then that would certainly impact, if you have a serious disease ... word not clear 01.58.25 these were things that were already existing and they were put into law, but they didn't innovate something...it was already there already...and the people that inspired the legislator already knew this from jurisprudence that existed at the time, so in that sense I mean that this is nothing new under the sun...sadly enough,

that that already existed and so it meant also that as it existed we took into account...we took those things into account.

I remember when I started working...I started working...I worked first in a refugee camp in Southeast Asia, so I saw vulnerability in another way, at a time, and so when I came back to Belgium, that was the time of the early 80s and you had all the huge impact from Southeast Asia, you had Pinochet and so on...all the people from Latin America who have been very severely tortured to come up from prison. How could you not have taken that into account? That it's not possible...but, of course, we didn't have many children at the time, they usually still came with their parents... the first children we really have was because of the war between Iraq and Iran when the parents, the Iranian parents wanted to bring their children, their sons into safety...a lot of the parents just dropped them into the airport and then took the next flight back home, it still happens, but we don't know that now anymore, they are unaccompanied minors, but that's what happened...but that is another thing, but as I said, at the time, we heard, I was working for UNHCR, so we were doing then the work that the Commission General later did...so we interviewed all these people...so yes, we heard so many of these terrible stories, of course we took that into account... how we could not have? So in that sense, you know, the only good thing now is that it's clear for everybody, even for those who do not want to listen and it is clear also that, as I said before, that for certain categories there is no question about it that they fall within the Convention, like gender cases so...in that sense LGBT cases are gender cases, depending on country they come from... and also what is very good is these procedural obligations, I think Belgium has done quite well compared to other countries, I think that the Commissioner general, when I see most of the work it is very well done, and, of course, things happen, but things happen everywhere... or somebody might not see what is exactly, or some person doesn't collaborate enough and there are always so many things around that but, at least, you can squash a decision out easily because the interview wasn't done correctly or...for instance... I squashed a decision once because the boy was in prison when he was 12 years old, but by the time he came here he was 18 and they questioned him on that.. on the prisons... they didn't doubt that he had been imprisoned for actually for a murder. He had...he was playing in the street with somebody else, he hit somebody and that boy died and we had all the proof of that which is terrible thing and he went to prison for that, but was 4 years or 2 years or something, but not so long and then he was set free, and I squash a decision because they interviewed him on these things as if he was an adult and I said he was 12 when that happened, you have to approach that at the time because that's how he experienced that and so you have this tools now in the procedural law that you can use for that... to squash in that sense... so it's...that's a very good thing, that's a very good thing. It means that the administrations have to organise themselves better, that they have to learn, that they have to keep learning and so on, so that study is really, really good. So even, as me personally, when I talk about myself I really talk about myself... that I'm not saying this could be the same for everybody else in the European Union...but...yeah...does that answer your question?

FR: yes, it does, thank you

KD: you are welcome

ZC: so do you have anything to add? Just to be clear

KD: not really, I don't think so, I don't know...except that I was wondering why you did not approach this more in the conflict between – no conflict, there is no conflict – but why...because you are talking, especially in your last questions, about the notion...and now again...

ZC: the 18?

KD: yeah...what notion are they talking about, you know, I was questioning that and then and...what different notion would you... yeah...I found a bit unhappy questions...

ZC: yeah, of course, I totally understand, it is a good point to mention, but to us was clear that we were referring to the categories, but we should be more...it is good that you mentioned that, so next time we will be more focused on the point...so it is clear

KD: yeah, all right, I didn't see it...yeah yeah. No, I don't know, if there is anything you want to ask, go ahead...

ZC: it is okay for us, I think we are done. We have just to thank you very much for having us today. It is very nice from you.

FR: thank you.

KD: you are welcome (...) I hope I have been of some use...

Glossary and List of Abbreviation:

Commission permanente de recours des réfugiés : the function of the *Commission permanente de recours des réfugiés* were transferred to the *Conseil du Contentieux des Etrangers* (CCE) since 1st 2007.

https://www.refworld.org/publisher/BEL_CPRR.html

<https://www.rvv-cce.be/fr/cce/historique>

CCE : *Conseil du contentieux des étrangers* (CEE) | *Raad voor Vreemdelingenbetwistingen* (RVV) | Council of Alien Law Litigation (CALL)

CGRA: *Commissaire général aux réfugiés et aux apatrides* (CGRA) | *Commissariaat-generaal voor de vluchtelingen en de staatlozen* (CGVS) | Commissioner-General for Refugees and Stateless Persons (CGRS)

CEAS: Common European Asylum System